

GREENGAGE

ENGAGING CITIZENS - MOBILIZING TECHNOLOGY - DELIVERING GREEN DEAL

Plan for the communication, dissemination and exploitation of results 3

Work Package 7, Deliverable D7.3

AWAITING VALIDATION BY THE EUROPEAN COMMISSION

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Glossary

Citizen Observatory	According to EU project WeObserve, “Citizen Observatories (COs) are community-based environmental monitoring and information systems, that invite individuals to share observations, typically via mobile phone or the web. Throughout these activities citizens become able to participate in environmental management/local governance.” [Reference: D2.1 - GREENGAGE Methodological Framework] In GREENGAGE is a place like a Living Lab (a laboratory in a real context, putting stakeholders at the centre of the process) for collective learning that exploits the opportunity of using sensors and the use of Earth observation technology where citizens collect data and are empowered by the information generated from these data to improve environmental management towards an innovative governance of the territory.
Citizen Science	“In Citizen Science, a broad network of people collaborates. Participants provide experimental data and facilities for researchers, raise new questions and co-create a new scientific culture. While they add value, volunteers acquire new learning and skills and gain a deeper understanding of the scientific work in appealing ways. As a result of this open, networked and transdisciplinary scenario, science-society-policy interactions are improved, leading in turn to a more democratic research, based on evidence and informed decision-making” (Socientize consortium, 2014, p. 10).
Citizen Science campaign	A Citizen Science (CS) Campaign comprises a period when a group of Citizen Observers with a shared mission and hypothesis gather data at different places and regularly get together to analyse together the correlation of their collected data with other external data sources to validate such hypothesis
GREENGAGE Academy	The GREENGAGE Academy hosts the emerging GREENGAGE Community of Practise and is the central platform for sharing understandings of the process of developing GREENGAGE COs. As such, the Academy serves as the central interaction platform between CO coordinators, Citizen Observers and other participants of COs. The Academy acts as a knowledge base and toolbox around the setting up and effective coordination of citizen observatories. The Academy stores and indexes training resources, MOOCs, success stories, findings and best practises collected from the four GREENGAGE pilots as well as generated or adapted to guide the setting up of the pilots.
GREENGAGE Citizen Observatory Methodological Framework	The GREENGAGE Citizen Observatory Methodological Framework suggests core concepts, processes and guidelines on how to develop Observatories in GREENGAGE in ways that are ethical, democratic and responsive to common urban challenges and their situational manifestations in GREENGAGE’s five Pilots.
GREENGAGE Engine	The GREENGAGE Engine is the set of tools and software applications that make up the GREENGAGE toolset. They will be used to support the GREENGAGE COs in fulfilling the objectives of the Innovation Pilots.
GREENGAGE Observatories	See Citizen Observatories. An update of the term Citizen Observatory to comply with equity, diversity, and inclusion frameworks, as some of the participants and target groups of these associations do not necessarily possess citizenship.
GREENGAGE Toolbox	The GREENGAGE Toolbox is the main stack of data processing and management tools. It comprises the set of tools within the “Data crowdsourcing and capture” and the “Data analysis and insights generation” layers of the GREEN Engine. Some of the tools included are MindView, MODE and HOPU apps, GREENGAGE app, Urban TEP/VISAT, Data Quality and Structure Dashboards, DIGITWIN, DataHub, Superset, Druid or NiFi.
Innovation Actions	Innovation Actions are "primarily consisting of activities directly aiming at producing plans and arrangements or designs for new, altered or improved products, processes or services. For this purpose they may include prototyping, testing, demonstrating, piloting, large-scale product validation and market replication. [...] Projects may include limited research and development activities” (EU HORIZON 2020). For GREENGAGE COs this means participatory research for

	innovation is not the focus but a means for understanding the GREENGAGE innovation action collectively.
Living Labs	According to the European Network of Living Labs, “Living Labs (LLs) are open innovation ecosystems in real-life environments using iterative feedback processes throughout a lifecycle approach of an innovation to create sustainable impact. They focus on co-creation, rapid prototyping & testing and scaling-up innovations & businesses, providing (different types of) joint-value to the involved stakeholders.”
Pilot Owner	The city or authority responsible for the implementation of a particular GREENGAGE innovation pilot.
Use cases	Generally, use cases are specific situations in which a product or service could potentially be used. In GREENGAGE we experiment in place-based, co-created and living platforms and learn about the useability of GREENGAGE COs as mediators of urban policy innovation. The products that are tested on their usefulness for driving transformative urban planning are existing technologies, tools and practices that brought into play by the GREENGAGE consortium to build tech-aided and co-created environmental monitoring and information systems, or GREENGAGE COs.

Executive summary (publishable)

GREENGAGE – Engaging Citizens – Mobilizing Technology – delivering Green Deal is a pan-European Innovation Action, funded under the Horizon Europe Framework Programme, that aims to promote innovative governance process and help public authorities in shaping their climate mitigation and adaptation policies. To achieve this aim, the GREENGAGE project leverages citizens’ participation and equips them with innovative digital solutions in order to transform citizen’s engagement and cities’ effectiveness in delivering the European Green Deal objectives for carbon neutral cities.

This deliverable concerns the *Plan for the communication, dissemination and exploitation of results*, which is integral to the **WP7 Communication, Dissemination, Valorisation and Exploitation**. This document provides an overview of all communication and dissemination activities within the project, along the guidelines to be followed by all the project partners. It details the methodology and the channels to be used for communication and dissemination, as well as detailing the expected timeline.

The GREENGAGE communication strategy will pursue the following objectives:

- *Raise public awareness and ensure maximum visibility of the project’s key facts, objectives, activities and findings;*
- *Announce and promote GREENGAGE Observatory campaigns and related public events to ensure a widespread engagement and attendance;*
- *Support the dissemination outputs.*

The GREENGAGE dissemination activities strive to ensure maximum visibility, accessibility and impact of the project activities. Ultimately, communication and dissemination activities will maximise GREENGAGE impact on prompting dialogues, cooperation, and coordination with the private business sector, the public sector (including policymakers), the academic community, Citizen Scientists, regional and local communities' sector, and local NGOs and associations who promotes sustainability measures.

The document also discusses the project’s Key Exploitable Results (KERs) and the way these are oriented towards assuring long-term exploitation of generated knowledge assets during and after the project lifetime.

This is a second version of the living document that will be regularly evaluated, updated and adapted in close collaboration with all project partners throughout the project lifetime and as new opportunities for communication, dissemination and exploitation arise.

Related documents

All GREENGAGE deliverables that are related to this document are listed below and are available at the GREENGAGE website <https://www.greengage-project.eu/knowledge-base/deliverables/>.

D3.2 CO solution mapping to pilots, recruitment and training report

D5.5 GREENGAGE CO Academy structured content 1

D7.1 Plan for the communication, dissemination and exploitation of results 1

D7.2 Plan for the communication, dissemination and exploitation of results 2

D7.4 Project identity and branding

D7.5 Project website and social media platforms

D7.6 Package of dissemination materials 1

D7.7 Package of dissemination materials 2

D7.8 Package of dissemination materials 3

D7.12 Citizen Observers’ exchange programme 1

1 GREENGAGE summary

The pan-European Innovation Action, funded under the Horizon Europe Framework Programme, aimed to promote innovative governance processes, and tried to help public authorities in shaping their climate mitigation and adaptation policies. To achieve this aim, the GREENGAGE project leveraged citizens' participation and equipped them with innovative digital solutions that shall transform citizen's engagement and cities' effectiveness in delivering the European Green Deal objectives for carbon neutral cities.

Focusing on mobility, air quality and healthy living, the aim was to inspire citizens to observe and co-create their cities by sensing their urban environments. The idea was to complement, validate, and enrich information in authoritative data held by the public administrations and public agencies. This was facilitated by engaging with citizens to co-create green initiatives and to develop Citizen Observatories (CO). In GREENGAGE, Citizen Observatories were and are a place where pilot cities co-examine environmental issues integrating novel bottom-up processes with top-down perspectives. This provides the basis to co-create and co-design innovative solutions to monitor environmental problems at ground level with the help of citizens.

With two interrelated project dimensions, the project aimed to enhance intelligence applied to city decision-making processes and governance by engaging with citizen observations integrated with Copernicus, Global Earth Observation System of Systems GEOSS, in-situ, and socio-economic intelligence, and by delivering innovative governance models based on novel toolboxes of decision-making methodologies and technologies.

The Citizens Observatory campaigns were deployed and fully demonstrated in 5 pilot engagements in selected European cities and regions including: Bristol (the United Kingdom), Copenhagen (Denmark), Turano Valley (Italy), Gerace (Italy) and the region of North Brabant (the Netherlands). These innovation pilots aimed to highlight the need for smart city governance by promoting citizen engagement, co-creation, as well as gathering new data which should complement existing datasets and evidence-based decision and policymaking.

Figure 1: Structure of project GREENGAGE.

2 Introduction

This Deliverable introduces the *Plan for the communication, dissemination and exploitation of results*, which is integral to **WP7 Communication, Dissemination, Valorisation and Exploitation** and covers tasks T7.1 and T7.2. This document is the third and final version of the communication, dissemination and exploitation roadmap (D7.1, D7.2), delivered in M3 (v01) and M24 (v02).

This plan outlines the GREENGAGE's comprehensive communication and dissemination strategy to be used by the consortium to ensure high visibility and promotion of the project and its results while focusing on a wide audience and to further maximize the impact of the project results. This plan also serves as a reference framework for evaluating the impact of project communication and dissemination outputs by providing effective evaluation metrics ensuring high communication and dissemination quality.

The plan also includes a comprehensive list of evaluation metrics for assessing and ensuring the communication and dissemination quality across different strategic domains. These are provided within Section 4.6 of this document.

This document has been regularly evaluated, updated and adapted in close collaboration with all project partners throughout the project lifetime and as new opportunities for communication, dissemination and exploitation arose.

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3 Target Audience

The GREENGAGE *Plan for the communication, dissemination and exploitation of results* targets a diverse audience. The aim is to tailor assets to the specific needs, interests, and communication preferences of each target group, maximizing the relevance and accessibility of the project's outputs to ensure long-term impact and value creation. The GREENGAGE project targets the following groups:

1. Local, Regional, and National Governments

- **Focus:** Emphasize the GREENGAGE's alignment with policy goals, such as European Green Deal, sustainable urban development, and climate resilience.
- **Approach:** Through our content creation we will highlight how the GREENGAGE's approach and methodology can inform evidence-based decision-making and improve governance outcomes. We will participate in public panels on critical and emerging topics to foster dialogue, raise awareness, and engage policymakers in meaningful discussions.

2. Local Communities

- **Focus:** Share relatable and practical information about how project outcomes will benefit their daily lives (e.g., cleaner environments, better infrastructure) and how they can get involved.
- **Approach:** While developing content, we will use accessible language and engaging formats like videos, social media posts, and local events to build trust and participation.

3. Civil Society (Initiatives, Environmental Agencies, NGOs)

- **Focus:** Showcase how the GREENGAGE project complements their missions and offers actionable insights or tools for advocacy and community action.
- **Approach:** While developing content, we will focus on knowledge exchange, specifically highlighting project-derived data and resources they can use to amplify their current efforts.

4. Academic and Research Communities

- **Focus:** Highlight methodological innovations, data, and findings that advance scientific understanding and academic discourse on Citizen Observatories and community engagement.
- **Approach:** We will publish results in peer-reviewed journals, present at conferences, and organize knowledge-building events such as workshops or seminars. We will facilitate access to open data and tools for further research.

5. Private Sector

- **Focus:** Showcase scalable technologies, tools, or models developed by the project, emphasizing their adaptability to different industries or markets.
- **Approach:** While developing content, we will highlight the GREEN Engine's potential for co-development, scalability, and adaptability.

6. European Commission and International Organizations

- **Focus:** Position the project as a contributor to global and regional agendas, such as the European Green Deal, UN Sustainable Development Goals, or climate adaptation strategies.
- **Approach:** Through our collective work, we will deliver high-level summaries and policy briefs, while also participating in international forums to highlight the scalability and transferability of results across regions and sectors.

4 Communication Plan

The GREENGAGE external communication actions are carefully charted to allow for the project objectives, activities and findings to be communicated in a concise and intelligible way to all relevant external stakeholders. Such an efficient publicity and wide exposure of GREENGAGE and its innovation aim to increase stakeholders' engagement with the GREENGAGE initiative, and to promote the use of GREENGAGE results beyond the project's lifetime. Together with dissemination activities, communication actions aim to prompt dialogues, cooperation, and coordination with the public sector (including policymakers), the academic community, the private business sector, Citizen Scientists, regional and local civic sector and local NGOs who promote sustainability measures.

The GREENGAGE communication strategy pursues the following objectives:

- *Raise public awareness and ensure maximum visibility of the project's key facts, objectives, activities and findings;*
- *Announce and promote GREENGAGE Observatory campaigns and related public events to ensure a widespread engagement and attendance;*
- *Support the dissemination outputs.*

4.1 Visual Project Identity and Branding

The visual project identity and branding is at the heart of establishing a coherent and consistent image of the project. With a pleasing yet impactful visual identity and style guide in place, GREENGAGE project becomes easily distinguishable and recognizable, a true promoter of green advocacy in line with the European Green Deal. Hence, the selected colour scheme is in the green spectrum.

ACTION PLAN

Starting from the GREENGAGE logo, which is delivered in M1, a number of variations are created to accommodate different needs (Figure 2): a simple horizontal version focusing on textual content (project name and tagline) and a compact squared version where textual content is enriched by a descriptive illustration. The horizontal version is to be used on official documents, where space is limited, or as a watermark over different mediums. The squared version is to be used on social media channels, digital banners and leaflets.

The visual styling is to be consistent across all supporting mediums: Word and PPT templates (Figure 3), digital banners (Figure 4) and leaflets. These are also delivered in M1 and shared with the project partners. A compliance to using the developed templates across the consortium is assured and well-documented. Figure 5 shows several internal (project meetings) and external (conference workshops) events where these templates were used and presented to the audience in attendance.

TARGET AUDIENCE

The visual project identity and branding targets all stakeholder groups listed in Section 3.

Figure 2: Different variations of GREENGAGE logos created for different application and needs.

Figure 3: Different GREENGAGE document templates created for different applications and needs.

Figure 4: GREENGAGE banner created for the website and used across LinkedIn and YouTube channels.

Figure 5: GREENGAGE PowerPoint template in use at internal (project meetings) and external (conference workshops) events.

4.2 GREENGAGE Website

The GREENGAGE website www.greengage-project.eu (Figure 6) is a core communication medium ensuring international visibility, communication and promotion activities. The website serves as an entry point for the external audience and the GREENGAGE Observers, providing comprehensive access to all project-related (e.g., aim, mission, objectives, partners, funding information) and pilot-related information, events and future developments. The website acts as a knowledge-sharing platform - it serves as a technology and knowledge base for GREENGAGE Observatories' (GOs), where participants of the GOs may gain knowledge and experience on using the tools from the GREEN Engine. Ongoing GO initiatives are promoted on the website, so that interested citizens who are not yet involved can take part.

ACTION PLAN

Website was publicly launched in M6. Specifically, the domain name and the landing page were live in M3, and additional content was developed by M6. Website development itself was overseen by AIT, in close collaboration with VRVis. The website was coded using a leading content management system – WordPress, further based on a DIVI design template. Hosting is maintained on the computer servers of DEUSTO. The technical maintenance is ensured by AIT and DEUSTO and the main content management by AIT and VRVis, with the ongoing contribution of all partners.

The website structure reflects the requirements of the project while maintaining user-friendly interface and navigation. The website holds a myriad of different assets and is able to accommodate text, images, infographics, audio and video materials based on deliverables and key findings from across GREENGAGE. It hosts engaging interactive multimedia (e.g., webinars, training sessions) developed within the GREENGAGE Academy that serves as a repository of freely available information, training materials, procedures and data that serves as a valuable resource for individuals interested in taking part in GREENGAGE Observatories. It has an online archive of project's scientific (e.g., scientific papers) and non-scientific (e.g., project deliverables) outputs. It contains a Blog section that reports on the valuable GREENGAGE achievements and provides insights into the latest project progress and developments. All partners were invited to provide an input in terms of making suggestions on the nature of content and the use of imagery. This content was curated by AIT and VRVis and uploaded online accordingly. This eliminated the possibility of damaging the website structure.

The website is considered a living platform that dynamically responds to the newly identified needs and requirements arising from the continuous dialogue with the Innovation Pilots within the Pilot Support Teams (PSTs). This was reflected on the recent restructuring of the website during M12-18. Specifically, each individual pilot page was tailored to its unique information and language needs, including bilingual content, and provides essential information on the pilot's background, aims, challenges, planned observatories, and relevant events. These pages also provide the GREENGAGE Observers with a possibility to register their interest in joining the ongoing and future pilot-specific initiatives.

Online forms facilitating an option to subscribe to an electronic newsletter and to access and download previous newsletter issues are available to a wider public use.

The project website will be maintained beyond the end of the project lifetime.

TARGET AUDIENCE

The GREENGAGE website targets all stakeholder groups listed in Section 3.

GREENGAGE

Become a GREENGAGE Observer | Access GREENGAGE Academy | Knowledge Base | Events | Blog | What is GREENGAGE?

ENGAGING CITIZENS MOBILIZING TECHNOLOGY DELIVERING THE GREEN DEAL

HEU INNOVATION ACTION

Strengthening urban governance by promoting citizen-based co-creation and crowd-sourcing

[PROJECT OVERVIEW](#)

GREENGAGE project sets out to help public authorities shape their climate mitigation and adaptation policies by engaging with citizens to co-create green initiatives.

To achieve this, the project aims at developing **GREENGAGE Observatories** focusing on mobility, air quality and healthy living for the delivery of carbon neutral neighbourhoods. The developed GREENGAGE Observatories are supported by **bespoke digital technologies and tools** that facilitate citizens' participation in observing, sensing, and monitoring their urban environments and co-developing innovative solutions to pressing environmental problems.

Findings are used to influence urban governance including policy evaluation, policy making and decision making at the city level.

GREENGAGE OBSERVATORIES

GREENGAGE Observatories are initiatives that empower citizens to actively participate in the collection, analysis, and interpretation of data to address various issues affecting their communities and contribute to policy-making and community development.

Five Innovation Pilots based at four European countries – **Bristol** (UK), **Copenhagen** (DK), **Gerace** (IT), **Turano** (IT), and **North Brabant** (NL) – are used to collectively respond to the GREENGAGE mission to define and deliver Observatories as integral components of decision-making processes that address current urban and regional planning challenges of climate mitigation and adaptation as well as healthy cities. They will demonstrate how top-down urban planning processes can actively intermediate novel bottom-up processes of multi-stakeholder engagement.

[LEARN MORE](#)

GREENGAGE ACADEMY

GREENGAGE Academy is a centralized repository of freely available information, training materials, procedures and data that serves as a valuable resource for individuals interested in taking part in GREENGAGE Observatories. The Academy is designed to enhance productivity and foster collaborative and continuous learning.

GREENGAGE Academy aligns with the broader mission of GREENGAGE Observatories by promoting environmental stewardship and sustainability. By equipping participants with the necessary skills and knowledge, the Academy empowers them to make meaningful contributions to environmental conservation and research initiatives.

[LEARN MORE](#)

Figure 6: GREENGAGE website landing page with navigation menu.

4.3 Project Promotion by the Partners

To further enhance the international visibility and promotion of the GREENGAGE project, all project partners will be asked to publish an announcement of the GREENGAGE project on their local websites or their local channels.

ACTION PLAN

When possibilities arose, GREENGAGE project was promoted on websites local to each project partner. Alternatively, project partners are continuously encouraged to promote GREENGAGE on their local media channels. Project partners announced the project and its scope on their platforms, examples:

AIT: <https://www.ait.ac.at/en/news-events/single-view/detail/7598?cHash=7a02a9c771fd040b04cc10de4342f349>

Sushi Dev: <https://sushi.dev/blog/eu-blockchain-projekt-in-bristol>

Digitalsunray: <https://www.digitalsunray.com/en/news/greengage-projekt-durch-b%C3%BCrgerbeteiligung-green-deal-ma%C3%9Fnahmen-unterst%C3%Bctzen>

I Borghi Italia: <https://borghipiubelliditalia.it/2023/09/29/i-borghipiubelli-ditalia-partecipano-al-progetto-greengage/>

MPA: <https://miljopunkt-amager.dk/thrive-zone-amager/>

BUas: <https://www.buas.nl/en/research/professorships/sustainable-transport-and-tourism/greengage>

UDEUSTO: <https://www.deusto.es/cs/Satellite/deustoresearch/en/home/top-research-outputs/international-research-projects#gsc.tab=0>

VRVis: <https://www.vrvis.at/en/research/research-projects/greengage>

IBERCIVIS: <https://ibercivis.es/tag/greengage/>

UWE: <https://blogs.uwe.ac.uk/research-business-innovation/uwe-bristol-success-within-horizon-europe/>

TARGET AUDIENCE

The project partner promotion of the GREENGAGE project targets all stakeholder groups listed in Section 3.

4.4 Social Media

A number of social media accounts are set up to help increase the public awareness, ensure maximum visibility of the project and keep up to date all interested parties about current activities. Specifically, GREENGAGE is spreading its messages and updates over LinkedIn, Instagram, and earlier also X (former Twitter), whereby these channels are used to reach different kinds of audiences and hence the messaging is adapted accordingly. Whenever possible, these tailored messages are enhanced with appealing visuals to help draw and capture attention of the public and gain followers who will further help spread the messages. These channels serve as accelerators to the discussion aligned with project objectives and activities and further serve as potential scouting medium for a widespread engagement.

ACTION PLAN

The initial setting up of social media channels was done by M3/M4. This specifically concerns channels such as X and LinkedIn. Other channels (i.e., Instagram) are established as the need and the opportunity arose, following project needs, communication priorities, and target audience dynamics. This adaptive approach ensured that each platform was launched when there was both sufficient content and strategic value, allowing the project to maintain an active and relevant online presence.

In order to plan the timely delivery of public messages, a collaborative social media planning and scheduling tool has been devised to effectively shape and schedule their dissemination over these channels.

X platform

X account is https://x.com/GREENGAGE_EU. It was set up in M4. This channel, in initial phases of the project, was used for short informative messages and news on the project supported by attention-catching visuals (pictures, banners, videos). We were also utilizing project-related descriptive hashtags (i.e., #GREENGAGEproject, #HEU, #citizenobservatory, #innovativegovernance, #citizendata, etc.) to establish a consistent presence and to integrate our discussions into a relevant existing context. However, at the later stages of the project, this channel was subsequently discontinued due to its limited added value to the project, as other channels of communication proved to be more effective.

LinkedIn platform

LinkedIn account is www.linkedin.com/company/greengage-project/ (Figure 7). LinkedIn account was set up in M3. This channel is focusing on creating dedicated communities discussing the specific topics. We aim for establishing a community on citizen engagement in urban data collection, among others. We also aim for connecting with relevant projects and initiatives to build synergies and foster knowledge transfer. Selected scientific articles, press media and other engaging content are also shared on this platform. The frequency of posts published by moderators in the group is foreseen to at least once per month.

Instagram platform

Instagram account is https://www.instagram.com/greengage_eu/ (Figure 8). The channel was set up in M29. The need for this platform emerged in the later stages of the project, aiming to engage audiences beyond the academic and corporate spheres. This channel is focusing on visually communicating the project's activities, milestones, and outcomes in a bite-sized, concise and accessible way. Through the use of engaging visuals, short videos, and infographics, it aims to raise awareness about the GREENGAGE initiative, highlight citizen participation, and connect with a broader audience beyond traditional stakeholders (e.g., targeting local influencers and bloggers).

Collaborative planning and scheduling tool

To timely and jointly plan our external messages, we set up a collaborative planning and scheduling tool where we coordinate communication activities, share content drafts, and align messaging across all partners (Figure 9). This tool enables real-time updates, ensures consistency in our outreach efforts, and arranges social media posts around selected topics, with specific topic leads assigned from within the consortium members to ensure effective coordination and content delivery.

Topics and their leads are assigned based on the expertise and respective involvement in other WPs. Specifically, the following topics and topic leads/supporters are assigned: 1) General announcements – VRVis/AIT; 2) GO Governance Framework – UWE/BUAS, AIT; 3) GO Pilots - KWMC/Pilots, PSTs; 4) GREEN Engine– DEUSTO/SushiDev; 5) GO Evaluation – AIT/UWE; 6) GO Academy – Ibercivis/KWMC; 7) Events (talks, synergies, CoCO) - Ibercivis/VRVis.

TARGET AUDIENCE

The public project communication via the GREENGAGE social media channels targets all stakeholder groups listed in Section 3.

GREENGAGE also strives to promote green advocacy by involving local influencers, bloggers and storytellers from different spheres (culture, art, fashion, etc.) that can provide a different angle of democratising the outcomes in line with the new European Bauhaus that connects the European Green Deal to our living spaces and to the enriching, sustainable and inclusive experiences. Such audience is reached through the GREENGAGE Instagram channel, as well as, channels local to each project partner. Through the connection with influencers, GREENGAGE indirectly utilized their personal social media profiles (e.g., Instagram) for spreading its messages.

GREENGAGE Project
 EU project supporting public authorities in shaping climate mitigation & adaptation policies through citizen engagement.
 Research Services · Vienna · 208 followers · 2-10 employees

Message Following More

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Overview

GREENGAGE aims to promote innovative governance process and help public authorities in shaping their climate mitigation and adaptation policies. To achieve this aim, the GREENGAGE project leverages citizens' participation and equips them with innovative digital solutions that will transform citizen's enga ... see more

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Reporting live from the DigiStreet exhibition at Technical Museum in Vienna 🚀🌱 ...more

GREENGAGE Project
 208 followers
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We are getting ready for tomorrow's Digital Days event at Technical Museum in Vienna, where we'll take part in the DigiStreet exhibition 🚀🌱 ...more

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Figure 7: LinkedIn landing page with the most recent posts.

Figure 8: Instagram profile page with the most recent posts.

Topic	Topic Leader	Topic Supporter	Planned Postings Date	Posted (✓/no)	Text LinkedIn (character limit up to 3000)	Text Twitter (character limit up to 280)	Notes
Events (talks, synergies, CoCO)	Nicolás Serrano (BERCIVIS)	Milena Vuckovic (VRVIS)	11/21/2023	✓	<p>Gear up for an upcoming pedal-powered revolution at the @BUas #CyclingLab Lunch Sessions organized within the #GREENGAGE project!</p> <p>Do you dream of a #bikecommute but face roadblocks? Interested in becoming a bike-fixing pro? Ever wondered about the psychology of your love (or lack thereof) for biking?</p> <p>The BUas team will tackle these burning issues on 5th December, 2023 at Sportsbar BUas within a series of enlightening lunch sessions designed to break down barriers and fuel our passion for cycling.</p> <p>These sessions are perfect for all biking enthusiasts out there, but also for a novice eager to try commuting on bike, or simply curious about the psychology behind bike choices!</p> <p>#BUasCyclingLab #BikeRevolution #GREENGAGE #ActiveMobility</p>	<p>Gear up for a pedal-powered revolution at the BUas Cycling Lab Lunch Sessions organized within the #GREENGAGE project!</p> <p>A series of enlightening lunch sessions designed to break down barriers and fuel your passion for cycling will happen on 5th December, 2023 at Sportsbar BUas.</p>	<p>to do: Tag people in the photo; location of the picture: https://atonline.sharepoint.com/:i/r/sites/HEUGREENGAGE337/Shared%20Documents/WP7%20Communication,%20Dissemination,%20Exploration/04_Plan%20for%20Communication,%20Dissemination,%20Exploration/Social%20Media%20Posts/CyclingLab.jpg?cf=1&web=1&embed=1&type=1</p>
CO Academy	Francisco Sanz (BERCIVIS)	Julia Costa Carneiro (KWMC)	7/3/2024	✓	<p>We're thrilled to share that we're in the midst of our "Training the Trainers" phase for our #GREENGAGEAcademy!</p> <p>We have had thought-provoking conversations on open data, remote sensing, co-design, air quality, and ethics as enablers of collaborative explorations of mobility, air quality, and healthy living. And there are still more themes to come!</p> <p>Through this work, we're meticulously building the GREENGAGE knowledge base and crafting top-notch training materials to ensure an unparalleled learning experience for future #GREENGAGEobservers.</p> <p>Stay tuned for more updates and opportunities to get involved! #TrainingTheTrainers #AcademyDevelopment</p>		<p>Location of graphics: https://atonline.sharepoint.com/:i/r/sites/HEUGREENGAGE337/Shared%20Documents/WP7%20Communication,%20Dissemination,%20Exploration/04_Plan%20for%20Communication,%20Dissemination,%20Exploration/Social%20Media%20Posts/CyclingLab_graphics_training.jpg?cf=1&web=1&embed=1&type=1</p>
Events (talks, synergies, CoCO)	Nicolás Serrano (BERCIVIS)	Milena Vuckovic (VRVIS)	19/7/2024	✓	<p>Exciting News!</p> <p>Our sister project CRObs is launching an open call for #CitizenObservatories and we're thrilled to support this incredible initiative!</p> <p>We believe that by combining our strengths, we can create a more impactful and comprehensive network of observatories.</p> <p>Find out more: https://citobs.eu/demonstrations-open-call-for-alliances/</p> <p>#CitizenScience #UrbanInnovation #SustainableCities #AirQuality #CoCreation #InclusiveCities #DataForGood #CommunityEngagement #Sustainability #Inclusivity</p>		

Figure 9: Collaborative planning and scheduling tool for coordination of external communication activities via GREENGAGE social media channels.

4.5 Digital Media

4.5.1 Press Releases

GREENGAGE strives to be well-represented in the digital (e-news) media local to each project partner.

ACTION PLAN

A set of press releases was prepared throughout the project lifetime for promotion and awareness rising about the project and its activities. The objective of this initiative was to inform on the project in a more detailed way, compared to what is achievable in the above-mentioned channels.

Press releases were drafted for selected key moments of the project. These included the most relevant information, presented in a concise and intelligible way. Press releases were prepared in local languages of each partner, and each partner is encouraged to push the publication in their local media. An example for the Copenhagen pilot is given in Figure 10.

TARGET AUDIENCE

The GREENGAGE press releases target all stakeholder groups listed in Section 3.

Figure 10: Sample of a press release for the Copenhagen pilot prepared for the local newspaper.

4.5.2 Interviews

Similarly to press releases, individual interviews focusing on many facets of individual project activities with involved project partners and GREENGAGE Observers were encouraged during the project lifetime.

ACTION PLAN

Each project partner and the participating GREENGAGE Observers were encouraged to contribute. Such interviews were either given to a local television channel or published via a local newspaper (digital or printed). The topics varied from the general information on the project to reflections on local challenges and ongoing activities.

Additional interviews were carried out during ongoing activities, such as datathons and ideathons. These interviews served to capture real-time perspectives from participants, organizers, and stakeholders,

highlighting experiences, lessons learned, and immediate outcomes. The collected material was then used for both internal reflection and external communication via the project’s YouTube channel (see Figure 15), helping to illustrate the human dimension of the project while strengthening outreach through testimonials and storytelling.

TARGET AUDIENCE

The GREENGAGE interviews target all stakeholder groups listed in Section 3, but especially the local communities that are expected to get informed on current campaigns, so that they can get engaged and participate in project-related activities.

Table 1: List of interviews

Organisation	Theme	Format	Period
BORGHI	Interview with Andrea Vignoli by the RAI (Radiotelevisione italiana)	Video Interview	January 2024
BORGHI	Interviews with local stakeholders in Turano Valley on local challenges	Video Interviews https://www.youtube.com/@BorghideITurano/videos https://www.greengage-project.eu/greengage-observatories/turano/	July 2024
IBERCIVIS	Interviews with local participants of the Turano Ideathon	Video Interviews https://www.youtube.com/@GREENGAGE-project/videos	March 2025
IBERCIVIS	Interviews with GREENGAGE pilot owners	Video Interviews https://www.youtube.com/@GREENGAGE-project/videos	March 2025

4.5.3 Digital Leaflets and Brochures

In addition to press releases, information on the project and its activities was provided via digital leaflets and brochures (please refer to the Deliverables D7.6, D7.7 and D7.8).

ACTION PLAN

Digital versions are available for download on the GREENGAGE website (<https://www.greengage-project.eu/knowledge-base/deliverables/>) and are frequently attached to a GREENGAGE newsletter or to a post on social media. Whenever a need arose, these are also handed out in a printed physical format during citizen training campaigns, public events and talks, or during conferences and other events. However, the aim was to limit the number of printouts in order to be more environment friendly.

Along the general information on the project and its activities, these materials also depict the integral parts of the GREENGAGE toolbox (i.e., the GREEN Engine), where people may inform themselves on the considered technologies. This is presented using a visually-appealing and clear infographics.

TARGET AUDIENCE

The GREENGAGE digital leaflets and brochures target all stakeholder groups listed in Section 3, but especially the local communities that are expected to get informed on and interested in the project.

4.5.4 e-Newsletter

An electronic newsletter aims to inform interested parties about ongoing and upcoming project activities.

ACTION PLAN

E-Newsletters hold information about the ongoing and upcoming campaigns, events, webinars, etc., along the general progress of the project. The subscription to a newsletter is offered via a GREENGAGE website (Figure 11), whereby it is made clear that joining the GREENGAGE mailing list is optional. Once someone subscribes to the e-newsletter, they will receive a welcome email informing them on what they could expect in the future (Figure 12).

TARGET AUDIENCE

The GREENGAGE newsletters target all stakeholder groups listed in Section 3, but especially the local communities that are expected to get informed on current campaigns, so that they can get engaged and participate in project-related activities.

Figure 11: Sign-up form for the GREENGAGE newsletter on the project website.

Figure 12: Welcome email sent automatically once someone subscribes to the GREENGAGE mailing list.

4.5.5 Videos

There are different kinds of video materials generated during the project lifetime. The topics vary from the general information on the project to instructional videos on the GREENGAGE technology suite and other aspects (e.g., citizen science methodology, data quality and governance, data standards, etc.).

ACTION PLAN

Firstly, a short video was created presenting the project, its activities, objectives and impact in an easy to understand, visually appealing manner targeting wide, non-technical audience. The main video was produced in English language to attract a wider audience, while transcripts on different languages were provided to better connect with local audiences. Videos depicting interesting developments of the project, for example the use of GREENGAGE app, were created during different phases of the project lifetime. Additionally, interactive webinars presenting the GREENGAGE technology suite and related training activities were a way to communicate about the progress, methodologies, best practices and success stories (Figure 13). These are developed within the WP5 and in connection to the GREENGAGE Academy (see deliverable D5.5). GREENGAGE also supports creating video interviews on different topics with the voices of local citizens (Figure 14). Such content was made available on both the GREENGAGE website and the project-dedicated YouTube channel (Figure 15, <https://www.youtube.com/@GREENGAGE-project>).

TARGET AUDIENCE

The GREENGAGE general video targets all stakeholder groups listed in Section 3. The GREENGAGE webinars and training videos primarily target the local communities who are expected to get familiar with

the GREENGAGE methodology and tools. The GREENGAGE interviews target all stakeholder groups listed in Section 3, but especially the local communities which were and still are expected to obtain information on current campaigns so that they can get engaged and participate in project-related activities.

The screenshot displays the 'GREENGAGE ACADEMY' section of the website. At the top, there is a navigation bar with links: 'Become a GREENGAGE Observer!', 'Access GREENGAGE Academy', 'Knowledge Base', 'Events', 'Blog', and 'What is GREENGAGE?'. The main heading is 'GREENGAGE ACADEMY', followed by a sub-heading: 'We assist you in your journey to become a GREENGAGE Observer by sharing our expertise and knowledge on how to use the tools for data collection, inspection and analysis.' Below this is a green button labeled 'ACCESS THE ACADEMY'.

On the left side, there is a search bar and a filter menu. The filter menu includes 'Pilot' with options for Turano (14), Gerace (13), Noord Brabant (11), Bristol (11), and Copenhagen (11). The 'Theme' section includes checkboxes for Starting (0), End (0), Project Management (2), Data Quality and Standards (1), Regulations and ethics (1), Citizen science (1), Best Practices (2), Instructions (1), Engagement (1), Communication (1), Air quality (1), and Data management (2).

The main content area features four video thumbnails with green headers and icons representing people and data. The first video is titled 'Atmotube Pro Manual' and shows hands using a smartphone. The second is 'Training on Remote Sensing and Use Cases'. The third is 'Training on sensory data: from streets and the earth'. The fourth is 'Training On Location Based Mobility Data'.

Figure 13: Pre-recorded webinars made readily available on the GREENGAGE website as part of the GREENGAGE Academy.

The screenshot shows a video player on the GREENGAGE website. The video title is 'INTERVISTE CON I PARTECIPANTI ALL'OSSERVATORIO CITTADINO DELLA VALLE DEL TURANO'. The video frame shows a woman in a red top sitting in front of a window with a view of a green landscape. A play button is overlaid on the video. Below the video frame, there is a text overlay: 'How much could the National Recovery and Resilience Plan (PNRR) - Next Generation EU project, wanted and desired by Collalto Sabino together with the coordinator, the Municipality of Paganico Sabino and Castel di Tora, positively influence attractiveness?'. The website navigation bar at the top is identical to the previous screenshot.

Figure 14: Pre-recorded interviews with the GREENGAGE Observers made readily available on the GREENGAGE website.

Figure 15: Project-related YouTube channel with webinars and training videos generated throughout the GREENGAGE project.

4.6 Measurable Criteria for Effective Evaluation

The overview of the evaluation metrics, KPIs and their planned delivery dates are presented in the Table 2 below. The KPI evaluation states the status as of Dec 2025 (M36).

Table 2: Overview of the evaluation metrics, KPIs and their planned delivery dates

Planned Assets		Planned Delivery Month	Actual Delivery Month	KPI Evaluation	KPI Monitoring					
Project Visibility & Branding	Project visual identity & branding	M1	M1	Logos are actively and consistently used across the project consortium	Delivery month is met; Assets are consistently used across the project					
	Production of Word templates for deliverables & PowerPoint presentations	M1	M1	Templates are actively used across the project team	Delivery month is met; Assets are consistently used across the project					
Public Reach & Media Engagement	Project website	M2/M6	M2/M6	100-200 unique visitors expected each month	23-Jan	-	24-Jan	280	25-Jan	NA
					23-Feb	-	24-Feb	262	25-Feb	NA
					23-Mar	-	24-Mar	174	25-Mar	NA
					23-Apr	-	24-Apr	202	25-Apr	NA
					23-May	-	24-May	227	25-May	NA
					23-Jun	-	24-Jun	130	25-Jun	27
					23-Jul	-	24-Jul	3958	25-Jul	165
					23-Aug	-	24-Aug	252	25-Aug	78
					23-Sep	-	24-Sep	126	25-Sep	357
					24-Oct	118	24-Oct	511	25-Oct	425
					23-Nov	136	24-Nov	NA	25-Nov	629
					23-Dec	97	24-Dec	NA	25-Dec	142
	Social Media accounts	M3/M4	M3/M4	250/20 followers/reposts	<p><u>LinkedIn</u>: 283 followers / 16 reposts per post</p> <p><u>X</u>: 38 followers (discontinued)</p> <p><u>Instagram</u>: 40 followers</p>					
Production of online press releases and interviews	M1-M36	M1-M36	Quarterly	Project information on partner websites; first interviews with Observers are online; interviews with Pilot Owners are online; interviews with Ideathon participants are online; MPA reporting in local newspapers						
Production of quarterly e-Newsletters	M12-M36	M12-M36	Number of clicks on the provided links	Welcome email created and subsequent newsletters sent out						
Project Public Awareness	Production of digital leaflets and brochures	M1-M36	M6	Materials are actively used across the project consortium and pilots	Delivery month was met; Assets are consistently used across the project					
	Production of a promotional video trailer presenting the project	M6	M6	1000 number of views	Sample video was created					
	Production of webinars	M12-M36	M12-M36	50 attendees / views per Observatory	Individual training videos are online - YouTube Academy; many videos have 50 plus views					
Knowledge Transfer & Public Dissemination	Scientific publications	M12-M36	M12-M36	Publish 10 academic papers in high-impact journals/conferences by project completion	<p><u>Conference papers</u>: 10 published</p> <p>SpliTech 2024 (4), NESS 2024 (1), IDC 2024 (1), REALCORP 2025 (1), SpliTech 2025 (3)</p>					
					<p><u>Journals</u>: 2 published</p> <p>JCOMSS (1), Springer Nature (1)</p>					

	Workshops and knowledge transfer events	M12-M36	M12-M36	Conduct 8 knowledge transfer workshops	<u>12 workshops conducted:</u> Bristol Business Breakfast 2023, OLLD 2023, ECSA2024, NESS2024, OLLD 2024, EASST-4S 2024, Urban Hosts 2024, POLIS 2024, Digital Days Expo 2024, CHANGE NOW 2025, WAVES OF CHANGE 2025, SSPCR 2025
Collaboration & Networking	Joint activities with sister projects	M1-M36	M1-M36	Engage in 5 joint activities with sister projects	<u>4 (5) joint activities conducted:</u> EuroGEO workshop, ECSA workshop 2024, ECSA marketplace 2024, EURA 2025, ESCA 2026
	Collaboration with other networks	M1-M36	M1-M36	Establish collaboration with 3 relevant thematic networks	<u>4 collaborations initiated:</u> ECSA, EuroGEO, ESA, GEO
Advocacy Activities	Pilot's engagement in local debates	M18-M36	M18-M36	Pilots' participation in 3 public debates or discussions (either in-person events or through media)	Bristol: OLLD 2023, OLLD 2024, Urban Hosts 2024 Copenhagen: CHANGE NOW 2025, WAVES OF CHANGE 2025 North Brabant: POLIS 2024 Turano/Gerace: ECOMONDO 2024
	Pilot's engagement in creating and disseminating datastories	M18-M36	M18-M36	Create at least 3 datastories per pilot	Bristol: 5 datastories in Superset Copenhagen: 1 datastory in Superset
		M18-M36	M18-M36	Disseminate each datastory through at least 3 channels (social media, local media, community platforms)	North Brabant: - Turano/Gerace: 1 datastory in Superset
	GREENGAGE's engagement in governance innovation debates	M18-M36	M18-M36	Project representatives engage in at least 5 panels or presentations on urban governance innovation	<u>8 panels attended:</u> OLLD 2023, OLLD 2024, EASST-4S 2024, ECOMONDO 2024, POLIS 2024, CHANGE NOW 2025, WAVES OF CHANGE 2025, SSPCR 2025
	GREENGAGE's engagement in thematic discourses	M18-M36	M18-M36	Project representatives engage in at least 15 thematic events around key project themes	<u>19 events attended:</u> Bristol Business Breakfast 2023, OLLD 2023, ECSA2024, NESS2024, SpliTech 2024, OLLD 2024, EASST-4S 2024, Urban Hosts 2024, POLIS 2024, Digital Days Expo 2024, EuroGEO 2024, ECOMONDO 2024, CHANGE NOW 2025, WAVES OF CHANGE 2025, EURA 2025, REALCORP 2025, SpliTech 2025, SSPCR 2025, EuroGEO 2025
	Pilot's engagement in datathons	M18-M36	M18-M36	Project organizes at least 1 datathon per pilot	Bristol: Bristol Datathon, October 2025 Copenhagen: - North Brabant: Datathon vis Provincial Cycling Event Turano/Gerace: Turano Ideathon, March 2025
Replication, Upscaling & Sustainability	Exploring continuation and replication of efforts	M18-M36	M18-M36	Explore at least 3 opportunities for continuation and replication of project activities	<u>4 attempts made:</u> Application to IMPETUS Acceleration Call 2025; Data collection campaigns in Bilbao by DEUSTO (ES), Vienna by AIT (AT), Vienna by VRVis (AT)

4.6.1 Definition of individual KPIs

The KPIs listed in Table 2 serve as benchmarks for assessing the overall contribution of dissemination and communication activities to the project's objectives. Their measurement relies on both quantitative indicators such as website visits, social media interactions, event participation, number of publications, etc. and qualitative indicators such as overall compliance to usage and application of certain assets. The definition of each KPI, based on a shared intra-consortium understanding, and their individual evaluation method is provided below.

Project Visibility & Branding

1) Project visual identity & branding

A cohesive visual identity for the project, including logo design, color schemes, typography, and graphic elements. It serves to ensure consistent and recognizable branding across all communication materials, platforms, and stakeholder touchpoints, supporting the project's visibility, credibility, and engagement by conveying its values, objectives, and personality in a visually appealing and professional manner. The KPI is measured through the consistent use across the project consortium.

2) Production of Word templates for deliverables & PowerPoint presentations

Standardized templates for project documents and presentations, ensuring a consistent and professional appearance across all outputs. Templates include predefined styles, formatting, and visual elements aligned with the project's branding guidelines. The KPI is measured through the consistent use across the project consortium.

Public Reach & Media Engagement

1) Project website

The project's official website, serving as a central hub for information, updates, and public engagement, presenting the project's objectives, activities, partners, and results in a clear and accessible manner. It serves to support dissemination, visibility, and outreach by offering news, resources, and interactive features tailored to various audiences, including stakeholders, policymakers, and the general public. The KPI is measured through the monthly external website visitation.

2) Social Media accounts

The project's official social media presence on platforms such as LinkedIn and Instagram (X was discontinued during the project lifetime) serves to support real-time communication, community building, and broader outreach by sharing project news, events, results, and stakeholder engagement opportunities at local, national, and international levels. The KPI is measured through the overall external number of followers and the resulting engagement activity (e.g., number of reposts, likes, comments).

3) Production of online press releases and interviews

The digital press releases and interviews to communicate key project milestones, achievements, events, and insights. Tailored for media outlets, stakeholders, and the general public, these materials aim to raise awareness, generate interest, and highlight the project's impact. Professional writing, visual elements, and strategic timing aim to ensure that press content aligns with the project's branding and communication goals while reaching a broad and relevant audience. The KPI is measured through the frequency of content publishing.

4) Production of quarterly e-Newsletters

The quarterly newsletter that highlights the project's latest developments, activities, results, and upcoming events. Designed for stakeholders, partners, and interested audiences, the newsletter serves to ensure regular, structured communication and to foster ongoing engagement. Visually aligned with the project's branding, it serves as an accessible and informative tool to showcase progress, share insights, and maintain transparency throughout the project lifecycle. The KPI is measured through the number of clicks on the provided links.

Project Public Awareness

1) Production of digital leaflets and brochures

The visually engaging digital leaflets and brochures that present key aspects of the project in a concise and accessible format. These materials serve to promote the project at events and stakeholder meetings.

Aligned with the visual identity and communication strategy, they effectively convey the project's goals, activities, and benefits to diverse audiences, supporting outreach, awareness, and dissemination efforts. The KPI is measured through the consistent use across the consortium.

2) *Production of a promotional video trailer presenting the project*

A short, high-quality video trailer that introduces the project, its objectives, partners, and expected impact. It serves as a powerful promotional tool for use on the project website, social media, events, and stakeholder presentations, enhancing visibility and audience engagement. The KPI is measured through the number of views.

3) *Production of webinars*

Webinars serve as a platform for knowledge exchange, capacity building, and community engagement, often featuring expert speakers, live discussions, and Q&A sessions. Professionally produced and aligned with the project's communication strategy, webinars support visibility, transparency, and active participation from diverse audiences across regions and sectors. The KPI is measured through the number of views.

Knowledge Transfer & Public Dissemination

1) *Scientific publications*

Dissemination of peer-reviewed articles, conference papers, and research reports that document the project's methodologies, findings, and innovations. Scientific publications aim to contribute to the academic and professional knowledge base, ensuring rigorous validation and credibility. They support the project's impact by sharing insights with the broader research community, fostering collaboration, and informing policy and practice in relevant fields. The KPI is measured through the total number of published papers. The publications are available on the project's website (<https://www.greengage-project.eu/knowledge-base/publications/>) and project-related Zenodo repository (<https://zenodo.org/communities/greengage/records>).

2) *Workshops and knowledge transfer events*

Interactive sessions organized within external events designed to share expertise, project results, and best practices with stakeholders, partners, and target audiences. These workshops are meant to foster collaborative learning, capacity building, and the practical application of project insights. The KPI is measured through the total number of conducted sessions.

Collaboration & Networking

1) *Joint activities with sister projects*

Collaborative initiatives and coordinated efforts undertaken with sister projects to maximize synergies, share resources, and amplify impact. Joint activities may include co-organized events, shared communication campaigns, data exchange and collection campaigns, and aligned dissemination efforts. The KPI is measured through the total number of conducted joint activities.

2) *Collaboration with other networks*

Strategic engagement with external networks, alliances, and communities relevant to the project's themes and goals. Such collaborations aim to expand the project's reach, exchange knowledge, and foster mutual learning. Activities may include joint events, cross-promotion, participation in network meetings, and integration of project insights into broader initiatives. The KPI is measured through the total number of conducted collaborative activities.

Advocacy Activities

1) *Pilot's engagement in local discussions or debates*

The active participation of project pilot sites in local forums, public discussions, and policy debates relevant to the project's themes. These engagements aim to foster local ownership, build trust, and ensure that project outcomes are aligned with regional priorities. The KPI is measured through the total number of conducted activities.

2) *Pilot's engagement in creating and disseminating datastories*

The active participation of innovation pilots in co-developing and sharing data-driven narratives that illustrate observatory campaigns, key findings, trends, or impacts from the project. These data stories, shared through various formats such as visualizations, multimedia, or written narratives, serve to enhance transparency, foster engagement, and support evidence-based dialogue at the local level. The KPI is measured through the total number of created and shared data stories and related narratives.

3) *GREENGAGE's engagement in governance innovation debates*

GREENGAGE's active role in contributing to ongoing debates and dialogues around governance innovation, particularly in the context of participatory, data-driven, and sustainability-focused decision-making. Through conferences, policy roundtables, expert panels, and collaborative publications, GREENGAGE aim to share insights from its Citizen Observatory model and pilot experiences. The KPI is measured through the total number of contributions to the relevant global debates.

4) *GREENGAGE's engagement in thematic discourses*

GREENGAGE's active involvement in broader thematic discussions relevant to its core focus areas, such as climate resilience, environmental justice, digital innovation, and citizen participation. Through contributions to conferences, workshops, policy dialogues, and knowledge platforms, GREENGAGE aims to bring forward practical insights, pilot experiences, and research findings. The KPI is measured through the total number of contributions to the relevant thematic events.

5) *Pilot's engagement in datathons*

The participation of project innovation pilots in datathons. Pilots contribute local datasets, challenges, and context-specific knowledge, enabling meaningful problem-solving rooted in real-world conditions. The KPI is measured through the total number of datathons carried out at each innovation pilot.

Replication, Upscaling & Sustainability

1) *Exploring continuation and replication of efforts*

This category focuses on identifying opportunities to sustain and scale the project's outcomes beyond its formal duration. It involves assessing the potential for long-term impact, securing stakeholder commitment, and exploring funding or policy mechanisms to support ongoing activities. Additionally, it includes efforts to replicate successful approaches, tools, or methodologies in new contexts or regions. The KPI is measured through the total number of explored opportunities for continuation and replication of GREENGAGE efforts.

5 Dissemination Plan

The GREENGAGE dissemination channels and assets are selected to allow for the crucial key messages and outcomes of the project to be successfully communicated to the largest possible number of relevant stakeholders. Dissemination activities support all Work Packages (WPs) ensuring maximum visibility, accessibility and impact of the project activities. Tailored dissemination activities are designed to make the project outcomes visible and accessible to the different target stakeholders and end-users. Such external communication channels and assets consist of tools, methodologies and communication flows meticulously designed to address the external audience using three instruments: 1) *online and recorded channels and assets*; 2) *digital channels and assets*; 3) *physical channels and assets*. Dissemination channels denote all online and on-site mediums used to transmit and relay project outcomes to the target audiences. Dissemination assets denote all digital and printed material support used to convey relevant project content. GREENGAGE dissemination and communication actions (WP7) will be intrinsically linked to the exploitation of the project’s activities and results.

5.1 Online and Recorded Channels and Assets

5.1.1 Website

GREENGAGE website’s URL: www.greengage-project.eu

Online presence aimed to give GREENGAGE vast exposure on the internet and continues to support communication of the project outcomes to the wider audience.

ACTION PLAN

This started with the creation of the GREENGAGE website (landing page in M3 and fully deployable by M6) where the content and key information of the project is posted. As the GREENGAGE website also serves as a main communication channel, the essential structural and organizational points were covered in sub-section 4.2. From the dissemination point of view, website hosts all scientific publications generated throughout the project (Figure 16, <https://www.greengage-project.eu/knowledge-base/publications/>), along the project deliverables that are made public. Furthermore, all pre-recorded webinars and training videos are made available through the website, as part of the GREENGAGE Academy (see Figure 13, <https://www.greengage-project.eu/academy/>).

TARGET AUDIENCE

The GREENGAGE website targets all stakeholder groups listed in Section 3.

Figure 16: Project-related scientific contributions made readily available on the GREENGAGE website.

5.1.2 Webinars and Training Videos

Similarly to the video material prepared for the communication purposes, webinars and training videos are a way to disseminate the results, best practices and lessons learned from the carried campaigns. These materials were produced, in part, during our GREENGAGE training and onboarding video sessions carried out within the WP3, as seen in Figure 17 (see deliverable D3.2).

ACTION PLAN

Webinars and training videos are meant to complement the citizen training and data collection campaigns in both content and timeline. Webinars and training videos are produced and delivered on an on-going basis during the project lifetime. As already mentioned, these materials are made available through the GREENGAGE website, as part of the GREENGAGE Academy (see Figure 13, <https://www.greengage-project.eu/academy/>) and on our dedicated YouTube channel (see Figure 15, <https://www.youtube.com/@GREENGAGE-project>).

TARGET AUDIENCE

The GREENGAGE webinars and training videos primarily target the local communities who are expected to get familiar with the GREENGAGE methodology and tools.

Figure 17: GREENGAGE training and onboarding video sessions carried out within the WP3 activities.

5.2 Digital Channels and Assets

5.2.1 Project Public Deliverables

Over the entire project duration, consortium produced a wide range of official project deliverables. These serve to inform both the funding body and the general public on the progression and achievements of the project.

ACTION PLAN

Deliverables that were made public are displayed on the GREENGAGE website (Figure 18) within the resources area in order to disseminate the project excellence and generated knowledge as widely as possible (<https://www.greengage-project.eu/knowledge-base/deliverables/>). Additionally, these are also uploaded to a project-related Zenodo repository (<https://zenodo.org/communities/greengage/records>). All project deliverables are drafted using the templates generated at the beginning of the project (see subsection 4.1). Deliverables are posted online as soon as they are officially approved by the funding body. The ones that are still in the review process were posted online with a dedicated watermark indicating their transitional phase, which later will be exchanged with reviewed final versions. The newly released deliverables are further promoted via project-related social media accounts.

TARGET AUDIENCE

The GREENGAGE deliverables primarily target the European Commission and international organizations who may use the GREENGAGE results for future European research agendas or policy-making at broader levels. These materials may also support academic and research communities who may build on the data, methodologies, or technological innovations to further scientific applications.

ACTION PLAN

The first version of the White Book was released in M24 and the final version (see Figure 19), completely restructured and designed at the end of the project (M36). It is made publicly available on the GREENGAGE website and the Zenodo repository. The project consortium ensures that the White Book is tailored to policymakers and government officials at different levels, using concise, actionable language. The content highlights specific policy recommendations, GREENGAGE best practices, and scalable methods, approaches, and tools. These are communicated using clear infographics and visual summaries to enhance comprehension and retention of key insights. The White Book will be shared over the social media platforms, presented during key political events, forums, and working groups, and also during targeted policy workshops and briefing sessions for government representatives, focusing on actionable takeaways.

TARGET AUDIENCE

The GREENGAGE White Book targets the local, regional, and national governments, European Commission and international organizations, civil society, private sector, and academic and research communities, who may use the GREENGAGE-generated knowledge and know-how for future research agendas or policy-making at broader levels.

Figure 19: Two pages of the GREENGAGE White Book: cover page and list of content.

5.2.3 Scientific Output

Scientific output serves to inform a wider scientific community on the progress and achievements of the project. These are tailored to showcase different aspects of the planned activities, including but not limited to best practices examples, study reports and recommendation papers.

ACTION PLAN

Over the project duration, project partners committed to release 10-15 scientific publications in total to highly ranked journals and to well-known conferences. Each publication acknowledges the funding body and the project framework. As mentioned above, these are regularly published on the GREENGAGE website (Figure 16, <https://www.greengage-project.eu/knowledge-base/publications/>), as well as on a Zenodo platform (Figure 20, <https://zenodo.org/communities/greengage/>), an open-access repository

that ensures long-term preservation and discoverability of our work. Each publication is assigned a DOI (Digital Object Identifier) number, ensuring that our work is easily citable, permanently accessible and traceable for future reference. Table 3 lists the publications published to this date, along the upcoming contributions.

To timely plan for our scientific output, we have compiled a comprehensive list of relevant scientific publishers and scientific events (Figure 21). This is a living document that was regularly updated. We have also extended this table to include a consortium partner list, providing a clearer overview of which partners are interested in contributing, enabling us to better streamline the collaborative content development process.

TARGET AUDIENCE

The GREENGAGE scientific output primarily targets the academic and research communities who may build on the data, methodologies, or technological innovations to further scientific applications.

Figure 20: A dedicated GREENGAGE repository on Zenodo platform.

5	Leveraging LLMs for Smart Cities Qualitative Data Analysis ISBN: 978-3-031-87638-7	Elisa Covato, Kamran Soomro, Zaheer Khan, Muhammad Bilal, Sam Kirby, and Tom Yiangou	17th International Symposium on Intelligent Distributed Computing 2024
6	Towards a Methodological Framework for Citizen Observatories to Promote Inclusive Urban Governance DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.14711633	Julia Costa Carneiro, Milena Vuckovic, Anna Kozłowska, Nikolas Serrano, Zaheer Khan, Diego López-De-Ipiña, Jan Peters-Anders, David Ludlow, Sjors Martens, Rubén Sánchez-Corcuera, Andrii Khrystodulov, Dawid Wolosiuk, Ernst Gebetsroither-Geringer	16th NESS - Nordic Environmental Social Science Conference
7	Empowering Urban Transformation: The Role of Citizen Observatories in Inclusive and Data-Driven Governance DOI: 10.48494/REALCORP2025.7035	Anna Kozłowska, Milena Vuckovic, Zaheer Khan, Ernst Gebetsroither-Geringer, Elisa Covato, Sjors Martens, Francisco Sanz, Diego López-De-Ipiña, Jan Peters-Anders	REAL CORP 2025 – 30th International Conference on Urban Planning and Regional Development in the Information Society
8	Participatory Design of Visual Analytics Tools for Different Target Groups DOI: 10.24138/jcomss-2025-0009	Milena Vuckovic, Johanna Schmidt, Dawid Wolosiuk	Journal of Communications Software and Systems
9	An Exploratory Study of Digital Literacy and Proficiency Challenges in Citizen-Based Initiatives DOI: 10.23919/SpliTech65624.2025.11091710	Milena Vuckovic, Dawid Wolosiuk, Rubén Sánchez-Corcuera, Diego López-De-Ipiña	10th International Conference on Smart and Sustainable Technologies – SpliTech 2025
10	A Strategy for Enhancing Privacy and Usability of Crowdsourced Data DOI: 10.23919/SpliTech65624.2025.11091383	Dawid Wolosiuk, Milena Vuckovic, Jan Peters-Anders, Rubén Sánchez-Corcuera, Diego López-De-Ipiña, Felipe Borge Vergara	10th International Conference on Smart and Sustainable Technologies – SpliTech 2025
11	Validating a Citizen Observatories enabling Platform by completing a Citizen Science Loop DOI: 10.23919/SpliTech65624.2025.11091698	Diego López-De-Ipiña, Dawid Wolosiuk, Mikel Emaldi, Felipe Borge Vergara, Rubén Sánchez-Corcuera, Milena Vuckovic, Diego	10th International Conference on Smart and Sustainable Technologies – SpliTech 2025

		Casado-Mansilla, Jan Peters-Anders	
12	A Systems Thinking Approach to Inclusive Governance	Rana Habibi, Amanda Ramsay, Martin Zach, Barkha Javed, Zaheer Khan	Discover Global Society, Springer Nature

5.3 Physical Channels and Assets

5.3.1 Public Events and Science Talks

Public events and science talks help reach a wide audience but also hard-to-reach groups and minorities, promote scientific vocations without leaving anyone behind, promote the project and share the project outputs with the respective target audiences, facilitate valuable feedback from respective stakeholders, and provide ground for policy discussions.

ACTION PLAN

The project hosted a range of internal events and workshops aimed at raising awareness among targeted stakeholders (Figure 22). These events also serve as key avenues for recruiting and training participants for the GREENGAGE Observatories. Table 4 provides a detailed list of all internal GREENGAGE events held to date across the five Innovation Pilots, highlighting our multi-faceted approach to stakeholder involvement.

In addition to these internal initiatives, we actively sought and seek opportunities to engage broader audiences through participation in external public events (Figure 23). By targeting these external platforms, we aim to extend our outreach beyond the core stakeholders, fostering wider public interest and understanding of our project's objectives. These engagements (Table 5) are vital for establishing a network of informed and motivated individuals who can contribute to and benefit from our work on sustainable innovation and climate resilience.

TARGET AUDIENCE

The GREENGAGE engagement in public events target all stakeholder groups listed in Section 3.

Table 4: List of GREENGAGE events (workshops, dialogue cafes, meetings, etc.) organized internally by project partners.

	Name of Event	Organisation	Type of Event	Attendance
1	Bristol Citizens Observatory Activation Workshop, Bristol, UK	BCC, KWMC, UWE	Participatory workshop	10 attendees
2	Fietsersbond onboarding, Den-Bosch, NL	BUAs, Province of North Brabant	Stakeholder meeting	9 attendees
3	BUAs Cycling Lab: bridging the barriers of biking behaviour, Breda, NL	BUAs	Participatory workshop	20 attendees
4	Active citizenship for Turano Valley, Collato Sabino (Turano), IT	BORGHI	Participatory workshop	70 attendees
5	Villages united for the cultural and social regeneration of the Turano Valley, Castel di Tora, IT	BORGHI	Talk	70 attendees
6	Active citizenship for the regeneration of Gerace, Gerace, IT	BORGHI	Talk	9 attendees

7	Citizen Observatory Workshop in Gerace, Gerace, IT	BORGHI	Participatory workshop	19 attendees (3 online)
8	BUAs Cycling Lab – Recreational Cycling: Opportunities and Challenges, Breda, NL	BUAs	Participatory workshop	30 attendees
9	Citizen Observatory Workshop in Paganico Sabino, Turano, IT	BORGHI	Participatory workshop	24 attendees
10	Citizen Observatory Workshop: Exploring Air and Mobility in the Turano Valley and Gerace, Collato Sabino (Turano), IT	BORGHI	Participatory workshop	39 attendees (10 online)
11	Citizen Observatory in Turano: Delivery of the board dedicated to mobility, IT	BORGHI	Stakeholder meeting	4 attendees
12	Bristol Observatory Workshop with the Barton Hill-based youth group (6 sessions), Bristol, UK	BCC, UWE, KWMC	Participatory workshop	14-15 attendees per session; Wrap-up session 24 attendees including three local councillors
13	Citizen Observatory sessions with Redfield Educate Together (4 sessions), Bristol, UK	BCC, UWE	Participatory workshop	35 attendees per session
14	Stakeholder mapping meetings “tour” in Turano by Claudio Bordi and Maurizio Angeli Felicioni (Borghi più belli d’Italia) (4 sessions)	BORGHI	Stakeholder meeting - mapping	2, 13, 52, 13 attendees per session, respectively
15	Ideathon in Turano, Italy	BORGHI, IBERCIVIS, AIT, DigitalSunray, Sushi Dev, VRVis, DEUSTO, GISAT, UWE	Participatory workshop	-
16	Student project on mapping air quality data	MPA	Participatory workshop	4
17	North Brabant Provincial Cycling Tour Event	BUAS	Participatory workshop	20

Table 5: List of external events.

	Type of participation/Title of the talk	Authors	Event name
1	(NETWORKING EVENT/TALK) Innovative concept of GREENGAGE	Zaheer Khan, David Ludlow, Muhammad Bilal	Bristol Business Breakfast
2	(PLENARY SESSION) GREENGAGE introduction	Diego López-de-Ipiña	8th International Conference on Smart and Sustainable Technologies – SpliTech 2023
3	(PANEL DISCUSSION) KWMC’s Bristol Living Lab practice and a reflection on the strategic role of Living Labs in regional transitions	Carolyn Hassan, Julia Costa Carneiro, Annali Grimes	Open Living Lab Days 2023
4	(WORKSHOP) GREENGAGE - Promoting innovative governance and helping public authorities in shaping their climate mitigation and adaptation policies by engaging with citizens via Citizen Observatories	Jan Peters-Anders	EUROGEO WORKSHOP 2023
5	(JOINT WORKSHOP CitiObs, GREENGAGE, UrbanReLeaf) Exploring ways to Enhance Diversity and Inclusivity in Citizen Science	(GREENGAGE authors) Francisco Sanz, Judith Bielsa, Milena Vuckovic, Jan Peters-Anders, Anna Kozłowska, Julia Costa Carneiro	European Citizen Science Association Conference – ECSA 2024
6	(MARKETPLACE BOOTH, joint event between CitiObs, GREENGAGE, UrbanReLeaf) Empowering urban transformation in an era of rapid change: CitiObs, GREENGAGE and UrbanReLeaf	(GREENGAGE authors) Jan Peters-Anders, Francisco Sanz, Milena Vuckovic, Anna Kozłowska	European Citizen Science Association Conference – ECSA 2024
7	(WORKSHOP) Towards a Methodological Framework for Citizen Observatories to Promote Inclusive Urban Governance	Julia Costa Carneiro, Nicolás Serrano, Diego López-de-Ipiña, Milena Vuckovic, Zaheer Khan, Jan Peters-Anders, David Ludlow, Sjors Martens, Rubén Sánchez Corcuera, Andrii Khrystodulov, Dawid Wolosiuk, Ernst Gebetsroither-Geringer, Anna Kozłowska	16 th NESS – Nordic Environmental Social Science Conference
8	(PANEL DISCUSSION) Organising discursive interventions for transformative policy making: Collective Reflexion on GREENGAGE Observatories	Julia Costa Carneiro, Sjors Martens, Milena Vuckovic, Sabine Seymour, Fani Kostourou	EASST-4S 2024
9	(PLENARY SESSION) GREENGAGE Cycling Lab: Citizen observatories to propagate cycling in North Brabant	Sjors Martens	2024 Annual POLIS Conference

10	(PANEL DISCUSSION) Smart Communities: AI, Digital Transition, and Social Change / Co-creating Civic Innovation through Arts, Tech & Care	Julia Costa Carneiro	Open Living Lab Days 2024
11	(PANEL DISCUSSION) Smart Village, technology at the service of Italian villages: opportunities and applications	Andrea Vignoli	ECOMONDO 2024
12	(LIVE BRIEF) Designing Liveable Neighbourhoods together	Julia Costa Carneiro	Live Brief 2024
13	(PUBLIC ENGAGEMENT) Making Liveable Neighbourhoods together	Julia Costa Carneiro	Urban Hosts 2024
14	(PANEL DISCUSSION) Rethinking mobility in the Ørestad neighbourhood	Julia Costa Carneiro, Rasmus Reeh, Sabine Seymour	Change Now Forum 2025
15	(PANEL DISCUSSION) GREENGAGE approach around engagement	Sabine Seymour	Waves of Change 2025
16	(PANEL DISCUSSION) Advancing Smart Governance for Sustainable Urban Transformation through Citizen Observatories and Digital Collaboration across European Cities and Regions	Julia Costa Carneiro, Stephen Hall, Zaheer Khan, Milena Vuckovic, Anna Kozłowska, Nicolás Serrano, Diego López-de-Ipiña, Annali Grimes, Zach Martin, Elisa Covato, Kamran Soomro, Jan Peters-Anders, Ernst Gebetsroither-Geringer	EURA 2025
17	(JOINT PANEL WITH SISTER PROJECTS) Empowering Smart Urban Governance through Citizen Observatories: EU Initiatives Driving Green and Digital Transformations for Sustainable Urban Futures	(GREENGAGE authors) Zaheer Khan, Julia Costa Carneiro, Samuel Green	EURA 2025
18	(WORKING SESSION) GREENGAGE Observatories concept and White Book	Anna Kozłowska, Jan Peters-Anders, Zaheer Khan, Francisco Sanz, Diego López-de-Ipiña	Smart and Sustainable Planning for Cities and Regions Conference 2025

Figure 22: Selected GREENGAGE events organized internally by project partners.

Figure 23: Selected external workshop events where GREENGAGE took part.

5.3.2 Policy Discussions and Synergy Events

The GREENGAGE project also targeted external events specifically designed to foster policy discussions. These events meant to bring together policymakers, public administrators, industry leaders, environmental agencies, earth observation officers, and other stakeholders to discuss regulatory frameworks, best practices, and collaborative strategies.

ACTION PLAN

We mapped relevant events that align with the project's goals and had the authority to influence policy change. The list of external events are listed in Table 6. Whenever possible, we organized workshops or breakout sessions focused on specific policy areas, while enabling exchange of the ideas, chart future action points, ensuring that policy discussions translate into actionable steps. By aligning on shared objectives and exploring policy impacts, we made sure that these sessions created a supportive environment for sustainable innovation, strengthen partnerships, and ensure that the project's outcomes

align with broader sustainability goals. At the same time, we are exploring synergy opportunities with our sister projects CitiObs (<https://citiobs.eu/>) and Urban Releaf (<https://urbanreleaf.eu/>) through joint policy-focused events.

TARGET AUDIENCE

The GREENGAGE engagement in public events to foster policy discussions primarily target local, regional, and national governments, civil societies, and European Commission and international organizations to inform and reform urban planning and environmental regulations.

Table 6: List of external events that foster policy discussions and sustainable change.

	Type of participation/Title of the talk	Authors	Event name	Synergy event with sister projects
1	(PANEL DISCUSSION) KWMC’s Bristol Living Lab practice and a reflection on the strategic role of Living Labs in regional transitions	Carolyn Hassan, Julia Costa Carneiro, Annali Grimes	Open Living Lab Days 2023	NO
2	(WORKSHOP) GREENGAGE - Promoting innovative governance and helping public authorities in shaping their climate mitigation and adaptation policies by engaging with citizens via Citizen Observatories	Jan Peters-Anders	EUROGEO WORKSHOP 2023	NO
3	(JOINT WORKSHOP CitiObs, GREENGAGE, UrbanReLeaf) Exploring ways to Enhance Diversity and Inclusivity in Citizen Science	(GREENGAGE authors) Francisco Sanz, Judith Bielsa, Milena Vuckovic, Jan Peters-Anders, Anna Kozłowska, Julia Costa Carneiro	European Citizen Science Association Conference – ECSA 2024	YES
4	(MARKETPLACE BOOTH) Empowering urban transformation in an era of rapid change: CitiObs, GREENGAGE and UrbanReLeaf	(GREENGAGE authors) Jan Peters-Anders, Francisco Sanz, Milena Vuckovic, Anna Kozłowska	European Citizen Science Association Conference – ECSA 2024	YES
5	(PANEL DISCUSSION) Organising discursive interventions for transformative policy making: Collective Reflexion on GREENGAGE Observatories	Julia Costa Carneiro, Sjors Martens, Milena Vuckovic, Sabine Seymour, Fani Kostourou	EASST-4S 2024	NO
6	(PLENARY SESSION) GREENGAGE Cycling Lab: Citizen observatories to propagate cycling in North Brabant	Sjors Martens	2024 Annual POLIS Conference	NO
7	(PANEL DISCUSSION) Smart Communities: AI, Digital Transition, and Social Change / Co-creating Civic Innovation through Arts, Tech & Care	Julia Costa Carneiro	Open Living Lab Days 2024	NO

8	(PANEL DISCUSSION) Smart Village, technology at the service of Italian villages: opportunities and applications	Andrea Vignoli	ECOMONDO 2024	NO
9	(PANEL DISCUSSION) Rethinking mobility in the Ørestad neighbourhood	Julia Costa Carneiro, Rasmus Reeh, Sabine Seymour	Change Now Form 2025	NO
10	(PANEL DISCUSSION) GREENGAGE approach around engagement	Sabine Seymour	Waves of Change 2025	NO
11	(PANEL DISCUSSION) Advancing Smart Governance for Sustainable Urban Transformation through Citizen Observatories and Digital Collaboration across European Cities and Regions	Julia Costa Carneiro, Stephen Hall, Zaheer Khan, Milena Vuckovic, Anna Kozłowska, Nicolás Serrano, Diego López-de-Ipiña, Annali Grimes, Zach Martin, Elisa Covato, Kamran Soomro, Jan Peters-Anders, Ernst Gebetsroither-Geringer	EURA 2025	NO
12	(JOINT PANEL WITH SISTER PROJECTS) Empowering Smart Urban Governance through Citizen Observatories: EU Initiatives Driving Green and Digital Transformations for Sustainable Urban Futures	(GREENGAGE authors) Zaheer Khan, Julia Costa Carneiro, Samuel Green	EURA 2025	YES
13	(WORKING SESSION) GREENGAGE Observatories concept and White Book	Anna Kozłowska	Smart and Sustainable Planning for Cities and Regions Conference 2025	NO

6 Exploitation Plan

GREENGAGE exploitation plan describes exploitation paths that were envisioned to safeguard the long-term sustainability after the end of the project. Efficient publicity and wide exposure of GREENGAGE and its innovation increased both the stakeholders' engagement with the GREENGAGE initiative and the use of GREENGAGE results beyond the project's lifetime and thus created value for stakeholders.

Together with communication and dissemination activities, exploitation strategy aimed to maximise GREENGAGE impact on prompting dialogues, cooperation, and coordination with the private business sector, the public sector (including policymakers), the academic community, Citizen Scientists, regional and local communities' sector and local NGOs and associations that promote sustainability measures (

Figure 24). It offered practical mechanisms for knowledge transfer, policy impact, and commercialization, ensuring that the project's outcomes were sustainably integrated into urban environmental management processes and continue delivering value well beyond the project's formal end.

The envisioned key exploitable results of GREENGAGE were, and remained, as follows:

- *KER1: The GREENGAGE CO Academy: Comprehensive knowledge base and training assets about COs ("knowing what") and practical application of this knowledge to increase the acceptance and the uptake for societal transformation of governance models ("knowing why").*
- *KER2: The GREENGAGE CO Methodology: Rigorous step-by-step methods to reach, engage, educate and involve society in performing observational and co-creation environmental thematic exploration activities ("knowing how-to").*
- *KER3: GREEN Engine and toolbox: A wide assortment of tools, sensors, software, platforms and guidelines to apply the GREENGAGE knowledge and toolbox, and accelerate its effective use ("knowing what & how").*
- *KER4: GREENGAGE Citizen Observatories: Document GREENGAGE innovative approach and raise awareness on how Citizen Observatories may give place to more effective urban policies facilitated by citizen participation to increase the acceptance and the uptake for societal transformation of governance models ("knowing why").*
- *KER5: A White Book for uptake and scale up of Citizen Observatories: General guidelines and principles on how to effectively setup, realize and run Citizen Observatories to ensure replicability of the GREENGAGE methodology, framework and outcomes, taking into account the demographic and cultural aspects ("scaling up").*

Figure 24: GREENGAGE exploitation roadmap.

6.1 Exploitation Mechanisms and Pathways

6.1.1 Capacity Building and Knowledge Transfer

The GREENGAGE project focused on maximizing the impact and long-term sustainability of capacity building and knowledge transfer efforts across two levels: 1) *Training and Workshops*, and 2) *Educational Programme*.

FIRST LEVEL

At the internal Training and Workshops level, the sessions primarily targeted the GREENGAGE Core Team members, consisting of consortium members, along with Observers in five distinct Innovation Pilots. These internal workshops aimed to equip participants with the necessary skills to effectively use the project's tools (KER3), data, and methodologies (KER2, KER4), fostering both local capacity and engagement. By building a strong foundation within this core group, we ensured that they are fully prepared to drive immediate, practical impacts within their communities. Once trained, participants were expected to serve as conduits for further knowledge dissemination, transferring their newfound expertise to broader networks and fostering a ripple effect of capacity building and knowledge sharing across communities and institutions. This strategy amplified the reach and longevity of the project's impact at multiple levels. Such an effect was made possible through the envisioned GREENGAGE Observer Ambassador Exchange Programme (see deliverable D7.12).

At the external Training and Workshops level, the sessions targeted all stakeholders identified in Section 3. These external events aimed to foster knowledge transfer beyond the consortium level, thus maximizing the impact and long-term sustainability of project's knowledge base, skills, and methodological approaches. These sessions served as opportunities to demonstrate cutting-edge tools, technologies, or methodologies developed by the project, fostering widespread awareness, interest, and adoption.

ACTION PLAN

Internal training and workshop sessions were collaboratively designed, prepared, and delivered as part of the GREENGAGE Academy programme (KER1), drawing on the consortium's broad expertise in areas such as data science, citizen science, data quality, data standards, and more (see Figure 17 and Table 4). The GREENGAGE website was the main channel assuring the long-term exploitation of these capacity building assets. All materials developed during the training programme were stored here with an open access with supporting information (cross-links) related to the GREENGAGE tools assets (see Figure 13). Furthermore, all of these materials were provided in different languages to help break the barriers to their utilization. The website was to be maintained for at least 24 months post-project completion, ensuring continued access and sustainability of these resources, while enabling ongoing engagement with GREENGAGE's methodologies and knowledge base.

All recorded webinars will remain available post-GREENGAGE also on a dedicated project-related YouTube channel (see Figure 15, <https://www.youtube.com/@GREENGAGE-project>).

External training and workshop sessions were strategically delivered during critical external events, such as conferences, congresses, and industry expos, to maximize outreach and impact (see Figure 23, Table 5 and Table 6). Hosting training at identified critical events ensured access to large, diverse audiences, including decision-makers, industry experts, researchers, and policymakers. They also provided a platform for stakeholders to connect, exchange ideas, and explore potential collaborations.

SECOND LEVEL

At the Educational Programme level, we envisioned integration of the project's methodologies and frameworks into research partner institutions' curricula for urban planning, environmental science, and citizen science. This approach was expected to shape a new generation of professionals, extending the project's impact into the academic and professional spheres.

ACTION PLAN

We were, together with our research partner institutions, continuously identifying specific courses where project methodologies could be incorporated, ensuring alignment with existing learning objectives and academic requirements. We were further investigating the potential for organizing guest lectures, workshops, and seminars led by project experts to provide students with hands-on experience and insights into real-world applications. Some of these activities are depicted in Table 7.

Table 7: List of educational engagement.

General content	Venue	Guest lecturer	Host lecturer
Active mobility, cycling barriers	BUas	-	Sjors Martens, BUas
Visual storytelling	Design school	Julia Costa Carneiro, KWMC	-

6.1.2 Open Science and Data Sharing

To ensure a long-term access to the GREENGAGE publicly available output, the utilization of renowned Open Science and Open Data portals was pursued. All activities in this direction employed FAIR principles to guarantee the Findability, Accessibility, Interoperability, and Reuse of digital assets.

ACTION PLAN

Open Science

We were publishing our scientific output under the open-access license and are making it freely and readily available via our project website (<https://www.greengage-project.eu/knowledge-base/publications/>) and other open research repositories, such as Open Science portal Zenodo (<https://zenodo.org/communities/greengage/>). A unique Zenodo Digital Object Identified (DOI) was assigned to all published records, which ensures an easy access and a global findability.

Open Data Repositories

All in-situ urban data collected during the project lifetime was made available on respective Open Data portals available to each city/region/country, ensuring it is equally available for further research, policy-making, and urban planning by other projects or institutions.

Specifically, these datasets were published on Zenodo along their accompanying metadata (the descriptive information about a resource), which was provided in an easy-to-understand format covering all essential aspects related to a resource (e.g., date of acquisition, location of origin, data type, etc.).

6.1.3 Commercialization

We were exploring several pathways for the commercialization of our innovations. By leveraging the project's cutting-edge tools, methodologies, and insights, we aimed to translate research into tangible market opportunities that drive impact across different sectors.

ACTION PLAN

Licensing of Tools/Software

We were exploring possibilities for offering monitoring tools, software platforms, or data analytics models to governments, private companies, and other entities under licensing agreements.

Service Provision

We were exploring possibilities for delivering consulting, training, or technical support services to organizations and cities seeking to implement the project's methodologies or technologies.

6.1.4 Policy Uptake

The GREENGAGE project was committed to ensuring its methodologies and findings influence and enhance policy development at all levels of governance. By engaging with policymakers and providing actionable resources, the project aimed to foster the integration of its outcomes into sustainable urban planning and climate governance.

ACTION PLAN

Strategic Policy Engagement

Active engagement with policymakers was pursued to strengthen collaboration with city authorities, regional governments, and EU institutions to promote the adoption of GREENGAGE policy recommendations. Our approach considered following aspects:

Stakeholder Mapping: We carried out a comprehensive stakeholder mapping within the WP3 activities, to identify key policymakers and institutions at local, regional, national levels relevant to our Innovation Pilots.

Direct Outreach: Through our consortium partners, and more specifically our Pilot owners, we were establishing communication channels with the identified stakeholder groups through personal meetings and tailored presentations to build relationships and ensure alignment with their policy priorities (see Table 4).

Policy Advocacy Events: We were actively organizing dedicated sessions during critical policy events, such as urban planning conferences, climate summits, and EU forums, to present findings and engage decision-makers in discussions about their practical applications (see Table 6).

Development of Policy Resources

We were also collectively working on creating and disseminating user-friendly resources that outline how to incorporate the project’s methodologies and frameworks into existing governance structures. Our central resource for policymakers was the White Book (see subsection 5.2.2).

6.2 Partner Contributions to Exploitation Pathways

The successful exploitation of GREENGAGE outcomes relied on the collective efforts and expertise of all project partners. Each partner played a crucial role in driving exploitation activities tailored to their expertise, networks, and operational contexts.

Table 8 outlines the exploitation and dissemination efforts of individual partners, detailing how these aligned with the project's overarching exploitation mechanisms and pathways described in section 6.1. The following classification was used to link these efforts to the overarching exploitation mechanisms and pathways: **KNOWLEDGE** – *Capacity Building and Knowledge Transfer*; **SCIENCE** – *Open Science and Data Sharing*; **MARKET** – *Commercialization*; **POLICY** – *Policy Uptake*.

Table 8: Overview of exploitation and dissemination efforts of individual partners.

Partner	Exploitation activities	Dissemination activities	Target exploitation pathway
AIT	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Further research activities Incorporation into AIT’s urban planning support services for different clients 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Scientific publications AIT’s Educational Programme Presentation at conferences 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> KNOWLEDGE SCIENCE MARKET
Sushi Dev	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Improving development landscape of the toolbox/chain Allow more features via our microservice landscapes Integrate more solutions from other partners 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Social media communication Blog posts Establishing new connections with potential partners (outside GREENGAGE) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> MARKET
DigitalSunray	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Further development of the toolbox Generating further research on sustainability, urban planning, safety Improving data-driven governance 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Promoting project outcomes and good practices at conferences Contribution to research on data-driven governance Educative workshops for governance units 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> KNOWLEDGE SCIENCE MARKET
Borghi	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Generating further research on village sustainability Positioning Italy’s rural heritage as a tourism asset, and enhancing sustainable strategies across networked communities 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Promoting project outcomes and good practices at cultural and tourism conferences Supporting sustainable tourism policy development, and 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> KNOWLEDGE SCIENCE POLICY

contributing to research on heritage-based tourism

MPA	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • New methods for citizens science • Further development of engagement and co-creation strategies 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Social media communication • Newspaper communication 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • KNOWLEDGE • SCIENCE • POLICY
BUas	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Data driven mobility research • Implementation and exploitation of knowledge in current (and new) policy networks and within Urban Living Lab Breda (with upscale potential to other living labs within the Netherlands) • Educational activities for bachelor/master and knowledge clips for industry • New applied research activities 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Conference contributions and presentations to governments and other stakeholders • Publications in scientific journals and magazines • Knowledge dissemination towards education • Support of the Breda policy agenda via the ULLB activities 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • KNOWLEDGE • SCIENCE • POLICY
North Brabant	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Incorporation of knowledge and developments in existing dashboard and tools • New methods for citizens science, improving data driven governance • Using knowledge for regional climate adaption and SDG goals 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Presentations at conferences • Workshops to support regional policy development and implementation 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • KNOWLEDGE • SCIENCE • POLICY
DEUSTO	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Open source licensing and consulting services based on it • Further research activities • Post project support services • Educational activities: case studies for undergrad and post-graduate students 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Scientific publications in reputable conferences and Journals • Presentations at public events, workshops and conferences, industrial fairs • Technology transfer training to local city innovation/technology unit 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • KNOWLEDGE • SCIENCE • MARKET • POLICY
Moondial	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Strengthen the expertise in using wearables in green tech • Launch new services 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Presentation of new technology at industrial fairs, conferences • Publications 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • KNOWLEDGE • SCIENCE • MARKET
GISAT	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Research activities on Remote Sensing related applications • Integration of solutions from other partners • Strengthen the expertise in Citizen Observatory domain 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Establishing new connections outside of the GREENGAGE consortium 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • KNOWLEDGE • SCIENCE • MARKET
VRVis	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Novel methods for educating and communicating environmental issues and related implications • Novel visual solutions for inspecting data quality issues • Further research activities 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Scientific publications in reputable Journals • Presentations at conferences and public events • Promotion of developed solutions at national/international events and with existing industry partners 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • KNOWLEDGE • SCIENCE • MARKET

IBERCIVIS	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Positioning of platform for international community of Citizen Observers platform Further development of engagement and co-creation strategies based on GREENGAGE Further research activities on data led pro-environmental initiatives Development of case studies for science communication and promotion of citizen science activities 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Scientific publications Presentation of results at workshops, network events, conferences Dissemination through educational activities 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> KNOWLEDGE SCIENCE POLICY
HOPU	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Open source licensing and consulting services based on it Public tenders IP and commercial exploitation Novel visual solutions for data quality issues Further collaboration with research institutions 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Scientific publications Presentation of results at workshops, network events and conferences Regular publication in social media and magazines 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> KNOWLEDGE SCIENCE MARKET
UWE	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> IP and commercial exploitation Further research activities Post project support services Educational activities: case studies for undergrad and post-graduate students 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Scientific publications in reputable conferences and Journals Presentations at public events, workshops and conferences, industrial fairs Technology transfer training to local city innovation/technology unit 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> KNOWLEDGE SCIENCE MARKET POLICY
Bristol	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> New methods for citizens science Further development of engagement and co-creation strategies 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Social media communication Blog posts 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> KNOWLEDGE SCIENCE POLICY
KWMC	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Novel application of Living Lab methodologies in context of policy and governance innovation Further research and innovation activities Further development of engagement and co-creation strategies based on GREENGAGE 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Scientific publications Presentation of project/use cases at workshops, network events, conferences and high public visibility events Dissemination through educational activities 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> KNOWLEDGE SCIENCE POLICY
MindEarth	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Further research activities Application of the implemented system towards addressing challenges alternative to those targeted during the project 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Scientific publications in reputable conferences and Journals Presentations at public events, workshops and conferences 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> KNOWLEDGE SCIENCE MARKET